

WORK OF RUSSIAN LOCAL SCHOOLS IN TURKESTAN.

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Abstract: This article talks about the influence of the Russification policy of the Russian Empire on the activities of schools in the Turkestan region, the organization of schools in the Russian system and the education system in these schools.

Key words: Turkestan, Central Asia, schools of the Russian system, Tashkent, Bukhara, Khiva, Samarkand, Fergana, Syrdarya, Auliaota, Nalivkin, Solikhodzha, Saidazimboy, district, village.

When the colonies of Russia came to Turkestan, its schools and madrasas, that are education places of local people, surprised them. The invaders got information about them and they realized that those schools and madrasas were so risky for activities related to colonization [Mansurov U., To`xtabayev A. -Page. 118]. The education system of the Russian Empire which consisted of Russification in Turkestan differed from another education system validated by the Russian Empire for people lived alongside the Volga River. Until the beginning of 80s, the main principle of the Russian Empire in the field of education had been to teach contemporary knowledge to local people`s children in only Russian schools. As a result, the official introduction of new schools was accelerated by local initiative [Abdullayeva M. -Page. 60-65]. In 19th December, 1884, a corresponding school opened in the courtyard of Said G`ani Azimboyev who was a son of a trader called Saidazam. In that school, V.P.Nalvinkin was confirmed as both the governor and Russian teacher, and also mullah Solixo`ja Kichkinaxojinov was confirmed as a teacher responsible for muslim classes. The Russian management found the local teacher as unequal as the Russian teacher, so it paid 1000 ruble for the Russian teacher and 400 ruble yearly for the local one. The Russian Empire`s schools were the first European language schools and they were available for local people to learn worldly knowledge. Goal of those schools was to prepare the low-level officials of the country`s administration from the native population`s children for the future.

In those schools, Russian was taught in the first year. The academic year was four years and study was not continued for more than 130 days every year, in some cases, it is recorded that it lasted for 250 days [Mansurov U.,

To`xtaboyev A. -Page. 119]. In countryside, students were busy doing tasks related to agriculture. That`s way the academic year ran late in autumn and finished early in spring, boys, who were 7 years old and up to 17, were taught in school and that type of school was begun to call “The Russian Empire`s Schools” [Qodirov N. – Page. 104-105]. In 1885, the Russian Empire`s schools began to spread to whole Turkestan. As a result, in autumn of that year, two of that kind of school opened in two villages, where were called Pskent and Chinoz, in Tashkent. As soon as the Empire announced command called “The changes in introduction of public education Turkestan” of state`s council, the establishment of the Russian Empire`s 14 schools at once showed what results the tsar`s administration in Turkestan expected from these schools. In the first years of operation of the Russian Empire`s schools, local residents did not send their children to this school. In order to supply the new schools with students, first of all, the children of the administration employees and wealthy people were involved. They, in turn, tried to appeal the children of the poor for certain fees [Qodirov N. -Page. 105-106].

From 1881 to 1914, there were only 160 Russian Empire`s schools operating in the territory of Uzbekistan, of which 135 were primary schools, 13 were upper primary schools, and 12 were secondary schools. 18,000 children studied there, of which nearly 5,000 were children of local nationalities. It was based on the idea that Uzbek and Tajik children studying in Russian Empire`s schools should be taught Islam so that their parents would not be afraid of these schools [Abdullayev M. -Page. 65-66]. According to the information provided by the academician Qori Niyoziy, in 1899, 4632 schools were operating in the regions of Syrdarya, Samarkand and Fergana alone. But these figures did not indicate that education in Central Asia has made any progress. According to statistics, in 1899, there were 44,773 students in all schools of Turkestan, that is, the average number of children studying in one school was less than 10 [Abdullayeva M. - Page. 65]. In such schools, the study day consisted of two parts, in the first part a two-hour lesson was conducted by a Russian teacher, and in the second part by an Uzbek teacher [Mansurov U, To`xtaboyev A. -Page 119]. In Russian Empire`s “local” class, the teacher had to learn the Arabic script necessarily to teach the students the Muslim religion, the Sharia, and the Qur`an [Abdullayeva M.-Page 66]. In 1887, a general program for Russian Empire`s schools was developed. Initially, there was not textbook system for these schools. As a result, the methods of teaching Russian language to Uzbek children were haphazard. As a result, few representatives of the local nationality left Russian Empire`s schools.

School-leavers usually read Russian very quickly and fluently, but could not memorize a single rule of Russian grammar, as a result of which they made serious mistakes in oral communication [Mansurov U, To`xtaboyeva A. -Page 119]. Later, the program and methodology of Russian language teaching in Russian Empire`s schools were designed for non-Russian students. In 1884, when Russian Empires schools were opened for testing, the Uzbek language was introduced for the students in the Russian section of the Turkestan Teacher`s Seminary. V.P.Nalivkin, who learned the Uzbek language well, was the first teacher who taught the Uzbek language in this school. Nalivkin taught at the seminary until 1890, before the opening of Russian empire`s schools in the early 80s, free Russian language courses were organized for older local residents at some Russian primary schools. In 1880, the primary Russian school in Avliyoota [now Jambul] took the initiative in this matter. Later, Russian language courses were opened at Russian educational institutes in the cities of the Fergana Valley. Such courses were opened in the school year 1884-1885 near Russian Empire`s schools all over Turkestan [Abdullayeva M. -Page 67-68]. At the end of the 19th century, there were more than 100 Russian Empire`s schools in Turkestan, and the Khan`s capitals opened Russian Empire`s schools in Khiva 1891, and in Bukhara in 1894 [Mansurov. U, To`xtaboyeva. A. -Page 120-121]. At that time, in some cities and volosts, wealthy and prestigious families knew the benefits of educating their children in Russian Empire`s schools. For example, out of 14 local students who left Tashkent schools in 1892, 3 were children of large landowners, 4 were children of merchants, 1 was a child of contractor, 1 was a child of mullah, 1 was a child of a family that had teahouse, 1 was a child of a miller, 1 was a child of shoemaker, 1 was a child of manager and 1 was a child of a teacher. 45, 82 and 89 Russian Empire`s schools were operating in 1901, 1905 and 1911 respectively in Turkestan. The colonial administration did not plan to educate the mass of the local population of Central Asia in Russian Empire`s schools. Perhaps they aimed to train a certain number of literate people serving in the lower positions of the country`s administration [Qodirov. N. -Page 106-108-114]. The development of national education, science and culture did not stop in the country at the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century. However, even in this matter, the historians of the soviet era in their works praised the policy of education, science and culture conducted during the Russian Empire, until the Russian invasion, they humiliated the situation in the country and hit the ground. In 1897, the number of literate Uzbeks in the country was 1.6%, Kazakhs - 1%, Turkmens - 0.7%, Kyrgyz - 0.6%. Literacy of

the population did not increase in the following years. They claimed that 98 out of 100 people in Uzbekistan were illiterate. [Mansurov. U, To`xtaboyeva A. –Page 120-121]. In 1897, only 1.9 per cent of Uzbeks knew how to read and sign. In 1897, according to the all Russian population census, the literate population in the country was 1.8%, that is, before the revolution, Turkestan was a completely illiterate country. “The Uzbek people were almost completely illiterate.” Even some scholars praised merchants like Saidazimboy, who betrayed his country and people and passed the invaders of Russia , saying that he opened a Russian Empire`s school in his house in Tashkent. In fact, Russian Empire`s schools were established to train translators [Mansurov. U, To`xtaboyev. A. –Page 120-121].

Summary:

In short, the purpose of the Russians to open Russian Empire`s schools in the Turkestan region was to train personnel who could establish contact with them in the country. In addition, there was a loss of identity and national values of the young generation growing up among the population. Because at that time, along with Russian Empire`s schools, Jadidist schools were also starting to operate in Turkestan. They took this way so that there would be no ideas against the colonial oppression of the population in the country in the future.

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